

HUNGARY

Country Report on HEI types

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Updated March 2024

Hungary

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Hungary, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the Hungarian higher education system comprises three types of HEIs:

- Universities
- **Colleges** and Universities of Applied Sciences (non-university higher education institutions).

Universities (*egyetem*) are higher education institutions authorised to provide at least eight Bachelor and six Master programmes, offer doctoral programmes and award doctoral degrees, provided that at least sixty percent of their teaching and research staff employed directly or on a public service employment basis have a doctoral degree, operate students' academic workshops and are able to provide studies in foreign languages in some of the programmes. Universities are authorised to offer programmes in every educational cycle.

Colleges (*főiskola*) are tertiary institutions having at least one-third of their teaching and research staff employed directly on a public service employment basis and have a doctoral degree. While the large former colleges have recently been transformed into universities of applied sciences, due to the reference year 2020/2021 of this report, Universities of Applied Sciences are included in Colleges. Universities of Applied Sciences are tertiary institutions with at least four Bachelor's programmes and two Master's programmes and with at least two dual trainings (if its accreditation includes engineering, IT, agriculture, the natural sciences or business studies), having at least 45% of their teaching and research staff employed directly or on a public service employment basis have a doctoral degree, operate academic student workshops and are capable of offering foreign language courses at some of the departments.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Universities (*egyetem*) are mostly public institutions and have the right to award PhDs. In total, about half of all Hungarian HEIs are Universities and equivalent institutions. Colleges (*főiskola*), including the newly established

¹https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/eurydice/hungary/types-higher-education-institutions_en

Universities of Applied Sciences, account combined for almost half of all Hungarian HEIs, however, only two of them award PhDs.

Table 1 below provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. Universities (*egyetem*) are mostly public institutions and have the right to award PhDs. In total, about half of all Hungarian HEIs are Universities and equivalent institutions. Colleges (*főiskola*), including the newly established Universities of Applied Sciences, account combined for almost half of all Hungarian HEIs, however, only two of them award PhDs.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 20

Category		N	Public	Private	Private government-dependent	PhD awarding
College	<i>főiskola</i>	24	6	8	10	2
University	<i>egyetem</i>	27	19	4	4	25
Total		51	25	12	14	27

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Hungary's higher education and its evolution over time.

Figure 1 shows that the higher education system in Hungary is characterised by long historical roots, with many HEIs having been established already before 1930 (around 40%). The Sárospatak Theological Academy of the Reformed Church, the oldest Hungarian College, dates back to 1531, followed by the Debrecen Reformed Theological University founded in 1538. A total of 15 HEIs were founded before the 20th century, including 11 Universities and 4 Colleges. While between World War II and the year 1989 only three Universities and four Colleges were founded, a new expansion process started in 1990 which continues until today – most of the Colleges and 10 Universities have been founded since 1990. The two most recent foundations (except for the transformation of Colleges into Universities of Applied Sciences) in Hungary are the John von Neumann University and the University of Veterinary Medicine in 2016.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Students

In contrast to the number of institutions, in terms of the number of students enrolled, Universities account for 83% of all students and Colleges (*főiskola*) for the remaining 17% (see Figure 2). While almost one out of four Hungarian HEIs in ETER is private, these enrol only 7% of the students and, therefore, play a limited role in the national higher education system.

According to different institutional mandates, we also observe systematic differences between educational levels: Colleges account for 20% of the bachelor students, 7% of the master students while doctorates are within the remit of Universities

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Total students includes ISCED 5-7

Academic personnel and financial resources

As illustrated in Figure 3, in the year 2020, Universities account for almost 90% of the academic personnel of the whole HEI system, i.e., substantially more than their share of student.

Figure 3. Resources, academic personnel and total students enrolled by type of HEI, 2020

This broadly corresponds to the fact that Universities also have an important research function. Data on revenues and the composition of revenues is not available for Hungary.

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students (figure 4), data show a pattern of decrease in the number of enrolled students decreasing by 22% from 2011 to 2020 with a slight increase in the share for Universities from 75% to 83% of the students enrolled. The overall decrease is mainly related to the Hungarian demographic situation. However, since 2016, the total number of students in both institutional categories has largely stabilized.

Figure 4 Share of students enrolled by institutional type

Note: Data for the year 2012 is missing

In contrast to student figures, there is a slight uptick in the number of academic staff (as shown in Figure 5), leading to an enhancement in the student-to-teacher ratio. Similar to student trends, the proportion of university-based academic personnel has grown steadily from 83% in 2011 to 90% in 2020.

Figure 5. Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2011-2020

Note: Data for the year 2012 is missing

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